

Subhepatic Klebsiella Appendicular Abscess Presenting as A Vague Abdominal Pain in a 10-Year-Old Girl: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

A 10-year-old girl presented to the outpatient clinic with complaints of vague diffuse abdominal pain with nausea and vomiting for one day not associated with change in bowel habits, fever or jaundice. On day 3, the patient returned to outpatient clinic with improvement in nausea but persistence in the diffuse abdominal pain. She started developing fever spikes. Laboratory investigations revealed elevated total leukocyte count with otherwise normal routine. Typhidot, Widal, Hepatitis A and Dengue antigens were negative. Intravenous antibiotics of ceftriaxone 1 gram and amikacin 250 milligram per day in divided doses were started. On day 5, fever spikes continued and abdominal pain was localised to right upper quadrant. Tenderness in right upper quadrant was noted. An ultrasonography of abdomen was requested which showed a ill-defined hypo-echoic mass in the right upper quadrant was noted. A computed tomography scan of abdomen showed a perforated retrocecal and sub hepatic appendicitis with abscess formation. Surgical gastroenterology review was obtained. A diagnostic peritoneal lavage and drainage was done which showed about 100 ml of pus in the sub hepatic space. 24F drain was placed. IV Cefaperazone sulbactam and metronidazole were started. On Day 12 review ultrasound of abdomen showed no focal collection or bowel wall thickening. Surgical gastroenterology review was obtained and patient was found fit to be discharged.

Keywords: Abdominal pain; Vomiting; Surgery

INTRODUCTION

Appendicitis though a common entity can provide challenges in diagnosis due to its variable position.^[1] The appendix is very vulnerable to inflammation making it one of the most common causes of acute abdominal pain and a surgical emergency.

Sub-hepatic appendicitis is a rare entity and can produce a significant diagnostic conundrum.^[2] Sub hepatic appendicitis occurs when there is a degree of malrotation and failure to descent of the cecum. Due to its location, it can commonly mimic conditions causing upper abdominal pain such as hepatitis, cholecystitis, gastroenteritis, peptic ulcer and mesentric lymphadenitis.^[3] Appendicular abscess occurs in 2 – 10 % of patients

with appendicitis. Appendicular abscess may occur with recurrent episodes of abdominal pain often vague in presentation.^[4]

Children often present with vague symptoms of appendicitis making diagnosis difficult. Despite its high incidence, diagnosis is often delayed owing to the vague nature of the presentation with the commonest atypical features being lack of fever or absence of right lower quadrant pain.^[5] A delayed diagnosis may lead to perforation and abscess formation.

CASE PRESENTATION

10-year-old girl, otherwise healthy presented to the outpatient clinic with one-day history of nausea, vomiting, loss of appetite and a vague diffuse abdominal pain. Abdominal pain was vague, generalised dull aching with no variation with respect to food or time of day. The patient was treated symptomatically on OPD basis. Three days later, the patient came back with complaint of high grade fever since the night before. She still experienced a loss of appetite though she had significant improvement in nausea and vomiting. She still had complaints of vague diffuse abdominal pain.

On clinical examination, there were no signs of dehydration. She was not icteric. She had a temperature of 100.5 °F, pulse rate of 112 beats/min. Abdominal examination revealed no tenderness or any localising signs. No guarding or rigidity. Initial work up was ordered. Complete blood count showed a white blood cell count of 15.9×10^3 cells/mm³ with granulocyte (neutrophil) predominance. Typhoid screening was negative. Total bilirubin was within range and urine routine was found to be normal. Intravenous antibiotic therapy was initiated in view of the elevated white blood cell count with intravenous ceftriaxone 1gram and intravenous amikacin 250 mg per day.

Two days later, the patient continued to have fever spikes and generalised dull abdominal pain. On examination there were no signs of dehydration or icterus. She had a temperature of 101.5 °F, pulse rate of 110 beat/min. On abdominal examination, mild tenderness was seen in the right upper quadrant. Differentials considered were hepatitis, typhoid, gastroenteritis, cholecystitis and liver abscess. Laboratory investigations showed leucocytosis, a normal urine routine, Widal negative, enteric culture showing no growth. Ultrasound of the abdomen showed dilated bowel loops in right hypochondrium with an ill-defined mass. Focal free fluid was noted. Computed tomography of the abdomen showed possibility of perforated retrocecal and sub-hepatic appendicitis with appendicolith with abscess formation [Figures 1 and 2]. Patient was referred for surgical gastroenterology review.

Figure 1: Coronal CT scan of abdomen showing sub hepatic appendicolith with peri appendicular abscess formation

Figure 2: Sagittal CT abdomen showing dilated appendix in sub hepatic space with dilated bowel loops.

A provisional diagnosis of sub-hepatic appendicular abscess with mass formation was made and she was scheduled for laparoscopic peritoneal lavage and drainage. Intraoperatively about 100 ml of pus was drained over sub-hepatic space and sent for pus c/s. Terminal ileum, cecum and omentum was found to be clumped to form a mass. A fecolith of size 1x1 cm was present. Thorough peritoneal lavage was performed and a 24 F drain tube was kept in right iliac fossa. She was on NPO for 36 hours and later switched to liquid and semisolid diet. Patient was treated with intravenous fluids and intravenous antibiotics - cefaperazone sulbactam and metronidazole, analgesia and other supportive drugs. Post Operative period was uneventful. Review ultrasound abdomen on 5th post operative day showed no focal fluid collection or inflammatory changes or bowel wall thickening. After obtaining surgical gastroenterology review the drain was removed, wound was healthy, dressing applied and child was found fit to be discharged. Patient was discharged on 6th post operative day with oral antibiotics and supportive medication.

The pus culture and sensitivity showed numerous gram negative bacteria and a few pus cells. It grew klebsiella pneumoniae with moderate extended spectrum beta lactamase (ESBL) activity. Patient came in for review 10 days after discharge. She has no specific complaints. Wound site was healthy. Sutures were removed.

DISCUSSION

Acute appendicitis is one of the most common surgical emergencies in children. Though the most common location of appendix is retrocecal, it can be variable in nature. The atypical positioning of appendix can result in atypical and unusual symptoms which delays diagnosis hence can result in perforation and abscess formation.^[4] Sub-hepatic appendicitis is a rare entity which accounts for 0.08 to 1% of all cases according to various studies.^[4,6] Majority of the case reports in the literature mention sub-hepatic appendicitis in adults there are only few cases in paediatric age group. It is also worth noting that almost all cases either presented with abdominal tenderness either diffuse or in the right upper quadrant. The lack of abdominal signs and the vague presentation made the case a diagnostic challenge. The lack of acute symptoms and localising signs favoured the differential diagnosis. The subacute vague presentation contributed to the delay in diagnosis.

USG abdomen though suggested first has a high probability of misdiagnosis. When performed it added to diagnostic dilemma adding the possibility of hepatic abscess. CT later performed confirmed the diagnosis of perforated sub-hepatic appendicitis with abscess formation.

Though Klebsiella pneumoniae is emerging as a leading cause of intra-abdominal abscess formation, especially the liver^[7] it is seldom reported to cause appendicular abscess especially in paediatric age group with no risk factors. The extended spectrum beta lactamase activity of the Klebsiella species added challenges to treatment aspect as it rendered resistant to 2nd and 3rd generation cephalosporin which are widely used in treatment of intra abdominal infection.

CONCLUSION

Subacute sub-hepatic appendicitis is a rare condition and when presenting with atypical features makes it difficult to diagnose and treat. Timely treatment can prevent formation of appendicular abscess. A high index of clinical suspicion is needed along with early imaging to diagnose for prompt intervention.

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